

Supplementary Table ST4: Validation Strategies Comparison

Validation Strategy	Description	Prevalence	Risk of Data Leakage	Recommended For	Representative Studies
Temporal Split	Train on earlier data, validate/test	73% (72/99)	None (if strictly chronological)	ALL time series forecasting	S1, S3, S6, S8, S9, S17, S22, S27, S35, S42, S71, S93
Random Split	Random assignment of samples to	11% (11/99)	High (future data may leak into	NOT recommended for time series	S14, S16, S19, S29, S56, S69, S70, S89, S90, S94, S97
Cross-Validation (Standard)	K-fold partitioning with random	5% (5/99)	Moderate to High (if random)	Small datasets; NOT for time series without temporal	S26, S38, S44, S60, S99
Nested Cross-Validation	Inner loop for hyperparameter	3% (3/99)	Low (if temporal ordering preserved)	Hyperparameter tuning with limited data	S20, S38, S60
External / Geographic	Testing on stations or regions not	8% (8/99)	None (spatially independent)	Geographic generalization testing	S2, S14, S26, S30, S51, S63, S82, S97
Walk-Forward Validation	Expanding window that moves	2% (2/99)	None (preserves temporal order)	Multi-step forecasting; streaming data	S63, S67
Real-Time / Operational	Testing on operational data	3% (3/99)	None (truly out-of-sample)	Operational readiness assessment	S9, S31, S35